

Synthesis and spectroscopic studies of Cr^{III}, Fe^{III} and Co^{II} complexes of hexaazamacrocycles

R. N. Prasad*, Mala Mathur and Ashish Upadhyay

Department of Chemistry, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur-302 004, Rajasthan, India

E-mail : rnp_1949@yahoo.co.in

Manuscript received 20 February 2007, revised 13 September 2007, accepted 20 September 2007

Abstract : Complexes of the type [ML(NO₃)₃] and [CoL(NO₃)₂] [where M = Cr^{III}, Fe^{III} and L = macrocyclic ligands L¹, L² or L³] have been synthesized by template method involving 2 : 2 cyclocondensation of α-diketones with 1,5-diamino-3-azapentane. These complexes have been characterized by elemental analyses, conductances, magnetic moments, IR and electronic spectra.

Keywords : Macrocyclic complexes, transition metal complexes, magnetic moments, electronic spectra.

2,6-Diaminopyridine has been commonly used to synthesize polyazamacrocyclic complexes e.g. those of Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with macrocycles derived from 2,6-diaminopyridine and α-diketones¹ such as 2,3-butanedione or β-diketones² such as acetylacetone or benzoylacetone. Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of unsymmetrical N₄ and N₅ macrocycles have been synthesized by the template reaction of polyamine such as diethylenetriamine with o-aminobenzoic acid and haloalkanes^{3,4}. However, complexes of N₆ macrocycles derived from diethylenetriamine and α-diketones have not been reported so far. Hence, we report herein the synthesis and characterization of Cr^{III}, Fe^{III} and Co^{II} complexes of hexaazamacrocycles derived from 1,5-diamino-3-azapentane and α-diketones.

	R ¹	R ²
L ¹	CH ₃	n-C ₃ H ₇
L ²	C ₂ H ₅	C ₂ H ₅
L ³	p-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	p-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄

Fig. 1. Macrocyclic ligands

Co(NO₃)₂·6H₂O with 1,5-diamino-3-azapentane and 4,4'-dimethylbenzil, 3,4-hexanedione or 2,3-hexanedione in 1 : 2 : 2 molar ratios result in the formation of hexaazamacrocyclic complexes according to the general Scheme 1. All the complexes are insoluble in methanol, carbon tetrachloride, acetonitrile and nitrobenzene but are soluble in DMSO.

R ¹ = CH ₃	R ² = CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₃	L ¹
R ¹ = C ₂ H ₅	R ² = C ₂ H ₅	L ²
R ¹ = p-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	R ² = p-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	L ³
M	k	x
Cr	3	9
Fe	3	9
Co	2	6

Scheme 1. Synthesis of hexaazamacrocyclic complexes.

Results and discussion

The reactions of Fe(NO₃)₃·9H₂O, Cr(NO₃)₃·9H₂O or

Molar conductances : Molar conductances of the macrocyclic complexes are given in Table 1. Complexes

Table 1. Physical characteristics and analyses of hexaazamacrocyclic complexes^a

Compd. and Molecular formula	Colour and Decomp. temp. (°C)	Yield (%)	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)				Molar conductance (Ω ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹)	μ _{eff} (B.M.)
			C	H	N	M		
[CrL ^I](NO ₃) ₃	Grey	57	39.93	6.32	13.87	8.80	101	4.25
C ₂₀ H ₃₈ N ₆ Cr(NO ₃) ₃	115		(40.00)	(6.37)	(13.99)	(8.66)		
[CrL ^{II}](NO ₃) ₃	Purple	64	39.91	6.34	13.92	8.61	129	4.01
C ₂₀ H ₃₈ N ₆ Cr(NO ₃) ₃	128		(40.00)	(6.37)	(13.99)	(8.65)		
[CrL ^{III}](NO ₃) ₃	Green	85	56.55	5.43	10.08	6.17	137	3.95
C ₄₀ H ₄₆ N ₆ Cr(NO ₃) ₃	175		(56.59)	(5.46)	(9.90)	(6.12)		
[FeL ^I](NO ₃) ₃	Brown	56	39.71	6.29	13.98	9.35	127	6.00
C ₂₀ H ₃₈ N ₆ Fe(NO ₃) ₃	145		(39.74)	(6.33)	(13.90)	(9.23)		
[FeL ^{II}](NO ₃) ₃	Brown	44	39.72	6.31	13.82	9.34	113	6.13
C ₂₀ H ₃₈ N ₆ Fe(NO ₃) ₃	123		(39.74)	(6.33)	(13.90)	(9.24)		
[FeL ^{III}](NO ₃) ₃	Brown	41	56.32	5.41	9.79	6.58	105	6.24
C ₄₀ H ₄₆ N ₆ Fe(NO ₃) ₃	192		(56.34)	(5.43)	(9.85)	(6.54)		
[CoL ^I](NO ₃) ₂	Brown	68	43.99	7.00	15.22	10.65	80	4.30
C ₂₀ H ₃₈ N ₆ Co(NO ₃) ₂	125		(44.03)	(7.02)	(15.40)	(10.80)		
[CoL ^{II}](NO ₃) ₂	Brown	56	44.16	7.15	15.63	10.94	65	4.34
C ₂₀ H ₃₈ N ₆ Co(NO ₃) ₂	170		(44.03)	(7.02)	(15.40)	(10.80)		
[CoL ^{III}](NO ₃) ₂	Brown	41	60.49	5.82	10.63	7.47	70	4.60
C ₄₀ H ₄₆ N ₆ Co(NO ₃) ₂	172		(60.52)	(5.84)	(10.58)	(7.42)		

^aThe N values do not include nitrate nitrogen which is removed on treatment with H₂SO₄ in Kjeldahl's method.

of Cr^{III} and Fe^{III} exhibit molar conductances in the range 101–137 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹ indicating 3 : 1 electrolytic behaviour. Molar conductances of Co^{II} complexes are in the range 65–80 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹ suggesting 2 : 1 electrolytic behaviour⁵.

Infrared spectra : All the macrocyclic complexes exhibit a strong to medium intensity band in the region 1590–1609 cm⁻¹, which can be assigned to νC=N of coordinated CN. It has been reported that νC=N occurs at 1620 cm⁻¹ in Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of the macrocycles derived from triethylenetetramine and ethylacetoacetate⁶. No absorption band is observed at 1700 cm⁻¹, which further confirms the condensation of >C=O group of the ketone with the -NH₂ group of the polyamine. N–H bands in all the complexes occur in the region 3125–3312 cm⁻¹. Band at 3280 cm⁻¹ has been assigned to the coordinated NH stretching in heterobimetallic complexes of 14-membered hexaazamacrocyclic 1,8-dihydro-1,3,6,8,10,13-hexaazacyclotetradecane⁷. Absorption bands at 815–846 and 1370–1390 cm⁻¹ may be attributed to ionic nitrate. Ionic nitrate absorptions occurs at 720, 829 and 1380 cm⁻¹ for Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes of 1,4,8,11-tetramethyl-

1,4,8,11-tetraazacyclotetradecane⁸. The complexes of hexaazamacrocycles derived from 4,4'-dimethylbenzil show bands in the region 1500–1590 cm⁻¹ due to νC=C of phenyl group. For Cu^{II} complexes of 2,9-dimethyl-3,10-diphenyl[14]-1,4,8,11-tetraazacyclotetradeca-1,3,8,10-tetraene, Coltrain and Jackels⁹ have reported νC=C(sym) in the region 1569–1590 cm⁻¹.

Magnetic moments : The magnetic moments of the complexes are given in Table 1. μ_{eff} values for Cr^{III} complexes are observed in the range 3.95–4.25 B.M., which correspond to spin only value for three unpaired electrons and are consistent with octahedral geometry around the chromium ion. Magnetic moments of 3.9 and 4.1 B.M. for Cr^{III} complexes of macrocycles derived from 1,4,8,12-tetraazacyclopentadecane and anions of phthalimide or succinimide have been reported¹⁰. The magnetic moments of Fe^{III} complexes are observed in the range 6.00–6.24 B.M. indicating the high spin state of Fe^{III} with five unpaired electrons. For Fe^{III} complexes of the macrocycle derived from carbohydrazide and 2,6-diacetylpyridine, Rana *et al.*¹¹ have reported magnetic moments in the range 5.76–5.84 B.M. For Co^{II} complexes

the μ_{eff} values are in the range 4.30–4.60 B.M. corresponding to the high spin state of the metal ion. Higher values may be due to orbital contribution. Malik and coworkers³ have observed μ_{eff} values in the range 4.81–5.12 B.M. for Co^{II} complexes of a macrocycle derived from 2,3-butanedione and 2,6-diaminopyridine.

Electronic spectra: Diffuse reflectance spectra of Cr^{III} complexes exhibit four bands at 644, 596, 517 and 437 nm which may be assigned to ${}^4B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g$, ${}^4B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4B_{2g}$, ${}^4B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g(a)$ and ${}^4B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}$ transitions respectively, suggesting D_{4h} symmetry around the metal ion. C_{2v} symmetry, which exhibit only two major $d-d$ bands has been ruled out, while D_{4h} symmetry around Cr^{III} ion shows three to four $d-d$ transitions due to splitting of ${}^4T_{2g}$ and ${}^4T_{1g}$ terms¹².

Fe^{III} complexes show three weak bands at 640, 590 and 430 nm due to spin forbidden and partly allowed Laporte forbidden transitions. Distorted octahedral structure may be proposed on the basis of energy band (590 nm) which is due to splitting of ${}^4T_{1g}$ term¹³. The bands at 640 and 430 nm may be assigned to ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ transitions respectively assuming the effective symmetry to be D_{4h} ¹¹. Co^{II} complexes show three bands at 755(ν_1), 640(ν_2) and 600(ν_3) nm, which may be due to transition of electrons to ${}^4T_{2g}(\nu_1)$, ${}^4A_{2g}(\nu_2)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(P)(\nu_3)$ excited states from ${}^4T_{1g}$ ground state in an octahedral environment^{14,15}. The lower values of ν_1/ν_2 (~1.2) suggest distortion from the octahedral geometry.

Experimental

2,3-Hexanedione (Aldrich), 3,4-hexandione (Merck), 4,4'-dimethylbenzil (Aldrich), 1,5-diamino-3-azapentane (Fluka) were used as supplied. Cr(NO₃)₃·9H₂O, Fe(NO₃)₃·9H₂O and Co(NO₃)₂·6H₂O (all Fluka) were of A.R. grade.

Cr, Fe and Co were determined by standard methods. Nitrogen was determined by Kjeldahl's method. Magnetic measurements were carried out at room temperature (298 K) on a Guoy balance using Hg[Co(NCS)₄] as a calibrant. Molar conductances of 10⁻³ M solutions of the complexes in DMSO were determined by Systronics direct reading conductivity meter-304. The IR spectra (KBr) were recorded in the region 400–4000 cm⁻¹ on a Nicolet Magna-550 FT IR spectrophotometer. Diffuse reflectance spectra of solid complexes were recorded on a Varian Cary 5E UV-VIS-NIR spectrophotometer.

Synthesis of Cr^{III} complexes of hexaazamacrocycles: Cr(NO₃)₃·9H₂O (2.0 mmol, 0.80 g) was dissolved in ~25 ml hot *n*-butanol to give a green colour solution. To this, a hot solution of 3,4-hexanedione (4.0 mmol, 0.46 g in 20

ml hot *n*-butanol) was added. The colour of the solution becomes dark green. A hot solution of 1,5-diamino-3-azapentane (4.0 mmol, 0.41 g in 25 ml hot *n*-butanol) was added drop wise with constant stirring at 75–80 °C. Stirring was continued for 5–6 h maintaining the temperature at 75–80 °C during which purple coloured solid was formed. The solid obtained was filtered while hot, washed with hot *n*-butanol and dried under reduced pressure.

All the remaining complexes of Cr^{III}, Fe^{III} and Co^{II} have been synthesized using similar procedure involving cyclocondensation of 1,5-diamino-3-azapentane with 3,4-hexanedione, 2,3-hexanedione or 4,4'-dimethylbenzil.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the Head, Department of Chemistry, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur for facilities, Head, RSIC, IIT Madras, Chennai for diffuse reflectance spectra, Head, Chemistry Department, Banasthali Vidyapith, Banasthali, Rajasthan, for magnetic measurements and the Head, DRDO, Gwalior for carbon and hydrogen analyses. One of the author (A.U.) is thankful to the UGC, New Delhi for the award of Junior Research Fellowship.

References

1. T. A. Khan, S. S. Hasan, N. Jahan and K. S. Islam, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2000, **39**, 450.
2. M. Shakir, O. S. M. Nasman, A. K. Mohamed and S. P. Varkey, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1996, **35**, 710.
3. W. U. Malik, R. Bembli and R. Singh, *Polyhedron*, 1983, **2**, 369.
4. A. A. Adimado, R. C. Abaidoo and C. Bondzi, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1991, **16**, 407.
5. W. J. Geary, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1971, **7**, 81.
6. T. A. Khan, S. S. Hasan, A. K. Mohamed and M. Shakir, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1998, **37**, 1123.
7. S. Tabassum, S. H. Rafiqi, N. Nishat, F. Arjmand and S. Srivastava, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2001, **40**, 1237.
8. N. W. Alcock, E. H. Curson, N. Herron and P. Moore, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1979, 1987.
9. B. K. Coltrain and S. C. Jackels, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1981, **20**, 2032.
10. M. S. Islam and M. M. Uddin, *Polyhedron*, 1993, **12**, 423.
11. R. Saraswat and V. B. Rana, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1998, **75**, 493.
12. B. U. Nair, T. Ramasami and D. Ramaswamy, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1986, **25**, 51.
13. L. J. Boucher, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1974, **36**, 531.
14. S. Chandra and L. K. Gupta, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 2004, **60A**, 1563.
15. T. A. Khan, S. S. Hasan, N. Jahan, A. K. Mohamed and K. S. Islam, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2000, **39**, 1090.